

Am i still an anthropologist if i...A Poem

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Abstract:

Am i still an anthropologist if ... i Am Not Accademic, Am Not "Smart", Do Not Read (see: All about Love, 1999, bell hooks; conversations with Audre Lorde, Hall, 2004).

Express myself Through Song Started in music, Know more about a bass guitar, Pentatonic scale, Mode, Key, Then anthropology, Never heard of, Opacity

Am i still an anthropologist, If I Draw, Express my thoughts through, Film Stop motion notions, And rumination, Through, Innovation, And sound, Am not profound,

B

ring nothing new, Just am honest, About what, i've Been Through,

Use Queer sensibility, Because the ethnographic study, Is Of me

More concerned with, Creating, Change, Than running my brain, Coming up with new theories, And critique, Of things that live in the, Accademic, Circle, Circle, Round again

Love ideas, That are, Birthed, Born, Grow, And, Live, Outside of, A simple essay or journal
Want to share my work, Dedication, To eradication, Of misrepresentation, Of Queers
And make up, My, Own, Words, My own methods,

My own way of speaking, Theories and frameworks, (Read: jumping off points), With art,
Music, Sound, Games,

Make something that looks out, Hand stretched, Reaches, The "average person", Like Me
The non accademic, The kid just desperate to see, Queer Joy, And see things working,
See change, On TV, In the everyday world, And holds them tight, Gives them a toolbox, an
idea, a thought, A way, To fix, Things

Cos I know that's something that, i, Needed, And didn't see, Because it just lived in the,
University, And essays for smart people, And people that read, And never really made it into,
My, Head, Because accademia, And, Anthropology, Was far too clever for, Me
So am I still an, Anthropologist, If i resist the

Essay

Resist keeping things within the

University
Circle

And instead make, Basic shit, That takes, Queer, Theory, Audre Lorde, Queer sensibility,
Halberstam, To that gamer kid, Watcher of tv, And says "here, this is for you too"

Am i an anthropologist, Or is my work, My research, My projects, My films, My games
My animations, My drawings, My poems (apparently, or is this an essay?)
Just scribbles in a notebook, That happened to be created, In School work, Made for,
MA/PhD Visual Anthropology, Or are they, More, Than, That, Are my ideas, My plans, My
thoughts, My hope, To bring my work

Outside

of the inner circle, And actually, Make, Change,
Transform these theories, These ideas I've seen, Activate them and do, Something,
Actually do something, With these ideas, Actually worth something, They are worth,
something

Maybe I don't read, Anthropology, Never heard of opacity,
Maybe I don't write essays, Don't know what to say,
In a seminar after reading a paper, But who gives a shit,
Because I would rather use art, Use film,
And tackle
Break

down

Misrepresentation of my people, Bring them Queer Joy
Inspire Queer Joy, Heal them with care, And films, Art, Games, workshops,
Injected with care, Injected with love, Maybe that's what anthropology needs, say no more
to, ~~fly on the wall objectivity~~,

Maybe I can't get, kinship, Or culture Vs Nature, Or how to do ethnography, Without getting
involved, And feeling, Embracing, Emotions, Using emotions,
As genuine paths, (Thanks Audre Lorde),

Maybe
I
See
The
Poetry
Instead

The loving ruminations, Of

Interwoven with
Drawing
Those are my tools
My feelings

bell hooks
Audre Lorde
Toi Derricotte

Film
Animation
And so is my heart
My Queer sensibility

Maybe an essay, Should be
instead
a song

A drawing
A film
A poem
So it can be read
By those who don't read
And it can exact the change
I want to be
A part of

Fuck it
I am an anthropologist
A visual anthropologist
Film is my essay
I use my pen for drawing
That's my ethnography
I am my own study
And so are my community
The community I want to inspire
And remind
Through workshops and films
Radical softness
And emotional honesty
Self-care
Self preservation
(Thanks Audre Lorde)
Remind us
of our capacity
For Joy
Queer Joy
And love

I am an anthropologist
A non academic

Anarchistic
Anthropologist
That is
Me

